

Letter from the Editor

DR. PETER D. KAZARINOFF

*Department of Computing and Engineering, Portland Community College, 12000 SW 49th Ave,
Portland, OR 97219, USA*

Keywords: J ATE, Journal of Advanced Technological Education

© 2022 under the terms of the [J ATE Open Access Publishing Agreement](#)

Dear Technician Education Community:

Welcome to the Journal of Advanced Technological Education! Or, as we like to call it, J ATE. On behalf of our Editors, we are pleased to launch the inaugural issue of J ATE.

J ATE is a peer-reviewed technical journal focused on community college faculty and staff who work primarily with technician education. J ATE is a platform for dissemination of peer-reviewed work that furthers the development of technician education.

J ATE is cross-discipline. J ATE covers all technologies under the National Science Foundation (NSF) Advanced Technological Education (ATE) Program. An incomplete list of disciplines covered by J ATE is below:

- Micro Nano
- Biotechnology
- Autonomous Technology
- Cyber Security
- Advanced Manufacturing
- Earth Sciences
- Agriculture Technology
- Energy
- Welding

In addition, J ATE will publish articles on topics that cut across all technician education disciplines, such as:

- Evaluation
- Mentoring
- Undergraduate Research
- Applied Technician Education Research

This first issue of J ATE features three articles that highlight some of the sub-disciplines in our community. One of the articles is on Unmanned Aerial Systems. While Micro Nano Technology is the theme of the 2nd article. And, the third article is on student recruitment. We want to thank the authors, reviewers, editors, and journal staff for their hard work bringing these articles to the publication.

As Editor-in-Chief of J ATE, I want to introduce you to the J ATE Editorial Board. Please reach out to Editorial Board members with your J ATE article ideas, journal questions, or collaboration opportunities.

Associate Editor: Dr. Neda Habibi, University of North Texas
Associate Editor: Dr. Atilla Ozgur Cakmak, Grand Valley State University
Dr. Jared Ashcroft, Pasadena City College
Mel Cossette, Edmonds Community College

Dr. James S. Smith, Lecturer, Princeton University
 James Hewlett, Finger Lakes Community College
 Dr. Linnea A. Fletcher, Austin Community College
 Jonathan M. Beck, Northland Community and Technical College
 Zackary Nicklin, Northland Community and Technical College
 Dr. Wesley Sanders, Salt Lake Community College
 Robyn Ceurvorst, Eastern Iowa Community College
 Visiting Editor: Dr. Ismail Fidan, Tennessee Tech University

J ATE was born out of the National Micro Nano Technology Education Center (MNT-EC) in late 2019 and early 2021. J ATE grew from an idea to a fully realized peer-reviewed journal with the support of five National ATE Centers.

Table 1. National ATE Centers Supporting the Journal of Advanced Technological Education

Technology	Center	Principal Investigator
Micro Nano Technology	MNT-EC	Dr. Jared Ashcroft
Biotechnology	InnovATEBIO	Dr. Linnea Fletcher
Autonomous Technology	NCAT	Jon Beck
Cyber Security	NCyTE	Corrine Sands
Advanced Manufacturing	RCNGM	Dr. Karen Wosczyzna-Birch
Earth and Energy Technology	EARTH Center	Dr. Ellen Bluth

As new ATE National Centers are launched, J ATE will incorporate their expertise into its Editorial Board.

As we move into the winter and spring, I invite you to participate in our J ATE Community. We are looking for new authors to publish their work. We strive to build a cohort of reviewers from all the sub-disciplines represented in technician education. And we need your help as readers and networkers to share J ATE with your colleagues and students. We hope to work with you soon.

In Teaching and Learning,

Peter D. Kazarinoff
 Editor-in-Chief